

Scientific Publication Policy

WP3 Joint Research Projects

WP4 Joint Integrative Projects

Responsible Partner: INSA

Contributing partner: SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Starting Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	Scientific Publication Policy version 2
WP and task	WP4
Author	INSA
Other contributors	SVA
Due month of the report	-
Actual submission month	M37
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.;</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R Save date: 20-Jan-21
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s): JRP/JIP project leaders, PhD students and their supervisors</p>

One Health EJP Scientific Publication Policy

1. Introduction

This One Health EJP (OHEJP) Scientific Publication Policy sets out guidelines for written scientific outputs submitted via a peer-reviewed process under the OHEJP.

The main purpose of this policy is to guarantee that the OHEJP scientific outputs are published to the maximum possible scientific standard, using a coordinated and appropriate approach. This is important in order to standardize messages from the consortium, to ensure speedy publication of scientific results, to avoid conflicts of authorship, to be transparent about any conflicts of interest, and to take into account the legitimate interests of all parties and owners of scientific results. This approach will guarantee that all researchers benefit from their involvement to the OHEJP consortium.

The Scientific Publication Policy describes the flow of scientific publications, from their drafting to finalisation. The policy is based on the commitments made by parties in the H2020 Grant Agreement and the OHEJP Consortium Agreement provisions and the Uniform Requirements for Authorship listed above, as well as to procedures laid down in the OHEJP Data Management Plan.

In case of disputes related to this publication policy, the specific JRP/JIP Project Leader (PL) will be contacted to arrive at an agreement. If required, OHEJP WP3/WP4 Leaders and the OHEJP Coordination Team (CT) may also be informed; their assessment will be based on OHEJP consortium interests.

It is extra important to remember

- to publish gold or green open access; and
- to follow the project procedure to anchor the decision to publish results; and
- to acknowledge the OHEJP.

2. Definitions

According to the HORIZON 2020 online manual.

Green open access (self-archiving): the author, or a representative, archives (deposits) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication. Some publishers request that open access be granted only after an embargo period has elapsed. Open access to the publication must be ensured within at most 6 months.

Gold open access (open-access publishing): an article is immediately published in open access mode. In this model, the payment of publication costs is shifted away from subscribing readers.

3. Scope of the OHEJP Scientific Publication Policy

This policy covers **all types of scientific material published in a peer-reviewed process** such as research publications in scientific journals and other scientific materials e.g., conference abstracts. National publications should build on already published international results.

Press releases, leaflets, brochures, reports, and other public communications are not in the scope of the Scientific Publication Policy. In this case, the authors should read the Dissemination procedure as well as the Communication Strategy document to find out how to proceed.

4. Producing scientific publications

The OHEJP Project Management Team (PMT) encourages researchers to stimulate the publication of scientific articles and other outputs in order to widely (qualitatively and quantitatively) disseminate the findings of each JRP, JIP and PhD project, during the project. The aim is that within 12 months after the end of the project all outputs should be published.

It is mandatory that all partners publish OHEJP research as open access publications (gold or green), using scientific leading international peer-reviewed journals in the respective field of research. The gold open access is preferred to the green open access, since it allows immediate dissemination without an embargo period. Independently of chosen strategy, the article must be made publicly available at the latest 6 months after publication according to HORIZON 2020 rules. Some journals have a longer embargo period than 6 months, these journals should not be chosen for publication of OHEJP research work.

OHEJP partners must make every effort to disseminate results rapidly (as soon as they are publishable), in order to feed evidence into the tight timeframes under an evolving policy agenda.

The lead author of a OHEJP scientific publication should inform the specific JRP/JIP PL and all the remaining project participants well in advance of submission. No paper or abstract must be submitted nor published before all co-authors have reviewed the publication and given their formal written approval (using any media). Similarly, the PhD student must inform the supervisor and co-authors of the intention to prepare a scientific publication.

During the peer-review process and prior to submission of the final draft, all authors must be consulted on any changes to the publication through the lead author.

The same workflow should be followed by any non-project member of the OHEJP aiming to submit an OHEJP scientific publication. In this case the submission should be approved by the PMT.

N.B. Inform the JRP/JIP project leader about the date for when the embargo period ends and the publication fee. This information will be included in project reports.

5. Overview of other principles for publishing

The **Data Management Plan** (DMP) sets out the requirements for ensuring data confidentiality and integrity when handling data. The lead author is responsible for the individuals handling data in the production of a publication to ensure that these requirements are respected.

Thus, where the publication uses OHEJP data, as OHEJP consortium partners will have direct access to a list of studies and relevant metadata generated via OHEJP JRP, JIPs or PhD project data, the lead author must respect the procedures set out in the project specific DMP and the OHEJP overarching DMP in order to access the data (both documents can be found on the private space on the website). The lead author is responsible for ensuring that these procedures are correctly followed when using OHEJP data accessed via the OHEJP repository to support a publication or any conference abstract — contacting the data owner and/or data provider at least 30 days prior to submission of any articles for

publication, providing the title, abstract and author list — and must then invite the data owners to be co-authors of the publication (the data owner and/or data provider may propose a maximum of two co-authors).

Any project participant may object to a publication for patent reasons or to request deletion of a participant's Confidential Information. Such objection must be submitted in writing to the specific JRP/JIP PL within 15 days of notification. If this objection is approved by the PL, the publishing participant will modify the publication as requested for patent reasons and/or delete such other participant's confidential information from the intended publication.

6. Authorship

Following the Uniform Requirements for Authorship and Contributorship from the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (www.icmje.org), authorship credit is based on:

1. substantial contributions to conception and design, acquisition of data, or analysis and interpretation of data; and
2. drafting the article or revising it critically for important intellectual content; and
3. final approval of the version to be published.

For particular publications, consortium authorship can be used. The lead author can then add "*on behalf of One Health EJP/JRP/JIP/PhD project [acronym]*" at the end of the list of authors. This request may be made by the PL when providing feedback on the publication proposal. If the journal specifically refuses this mention in the authorship, it should be added in acknowledgments, and the web address for the OHEJP website should be cited.

7. Ethics

The authors must include text to confirm that all animal or human research has been conducted according to ethical legislations, even if this information is not explicitly requested by the journal. In addition, it should be stated that the OHEJP also has put in place a strict monitoring of the ethical issues and is bound to it through a precise check by external ethical advisors. The manuscript must follow the journal's requirements (e.g., ethical approval authorities and numbers).

8. Publication and Intellectual Property

All OHEJP participants are encouraged to publish results in a timely fashion (as soon as results are publishable). It is acceptable to delay publication to allow partners to achieve suitable Intellectual Property protection (see Section 5.5.6.2. of DMP from OHEJP). However, this delay is not allowed to be longer than the specified embargo period associated with the data being submitted, which might be from 6 to 12 months from the completion of the data analysis (see article 29.2 of Grant Agreement).

9. Disclosure information

If applicable, a statement about author's disclosure should be included in manuscripts, according to the guidelines of the journal.

10. Acknowledgements of EU funding and the OHEJP

All scientific publications that include or build on OHEJP results, data or materials must specify that the project has received EU research support and funding. Acknowledgement must be performed with the following text:

“This work was supported by funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 773830: One Health European Joint Programme.”

Note that:

- Where possible in publication types, the European Union flag should be included, and when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.
- Abstracts or papers partially including OHEJP data should mention it appropriately.
- In cases where OHEJP partners produce a publication that refers to OHEJP, but does not actually draw on results produced under the initiative, partners are asked to acknowledge OHEJP.
- Publications that are not the result of research carried out under the OHEJP project should not be acknowledged to OHEJP.
- The inclusion of OHEJP subjects in another study (abstract or manuscript) without sharing of data from OHEJP does not need any form of mention.

These instructions are independent of those of other financing organisations that may have provided funds for the research.

11. Archive and access to publications

The Scientific Publication Policy should be read in conjunction with the [Dissemination Procedure](#) and [Communication Strategy documents](#), e.g., in order to inform all OHEJP consortium partners about an accepted peer-reviewed publication in a scientific journal and to make it available on the One Health EJP website.

12. Consequences of non-compliance

For non-compliance, see article 29.6 and 43 of Grant Agreement, resulting of possible rejection of declared costs in relation with the publication and a reduction of the total EU Grant.